

A Circular Polarization patch array designed for a Sentinel-1 SAR transponder

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Abstract—This paper reports the design and preliminary test of a circular polarized patch array antenna operating in C band. The antenna was designed as part of a C band Active Corner reflector (ACR). The operating band is 5.405 GHz \pm 50 MHz band, the same used by ESA Sentinel-1 SAR. The main requirements for the antenna system are: a simple design to assure an adequate phase stability, simple installation, and low cost, as requested for the proposed ACR.

Index Terms—antenna, propagation, measurement.

I. INTRODUCTION

The dataset of SAR images for Earth observation in the last years drastically increased, and the Sentinel-1 mission, within the European Radar Observatory, designed and developed by ESA and funded by the EC (European Commission), has been contributing to the possibility of process polarimetric data, with a revisit time suitable to many applications among which the study of the cryosphere. The observation of this portion of the Earth surface with negligible effects of the meteorological status, and not affected by illumination conditions, providing a 24/7 availability typical of radar observation from the space, is contributing to different studies, including the hydrological balance and more generally the climate change. The use of SAR data to estimate geophysical parameters can benefit from the presence of benchmark in the image scene, represented by strong reflectors with accurate localization, for image interpretation, radiometric calibration, and phase stability check for interferometric applications.

The use of passive reflectors, as trihedral corner reflectors, in areas with limited or very hard accessibility as glaciers or snow covered zone is very difficult and costly. Recently, some Active Corner Reflector (ACR) have been manufactured by companies [1], but their cost is too high to allow a wide distribution of these devices for a massive use.

For this reason, the development of ACR with simpler installation procedures, handy, and low cost, in spite of reducing some performances for an operational use, has started within an Innovation action of H2020 framework [2].

In this device the receiving and transmitting antenna have a critical role, and the transceiver proposed by the authors uses Circular Polarization (CP) to provide a signal for both co- and cross linear polarizations of the satellite, and reduce the installation critical issue. In the following the main characteristics of a Circular polarized patch array designed for this specific application are discussed. The paper mainly reports the results of the simulations because the test of the prototype, implemented just contemporary to the writing of this paper, has not been completed.

II. THE DESIGN

Design choice and expected performances

The design of CP antenna arrays can be made using different approaches: composed of individual CP elements, or linearly polarized (LP) elements [3][4][5]. The first choice demands a careful design of feed line, while the second is in general easier. In addition, a variety of CP elements is available. The goal of the design is a 2x2 array with circular polarized patches. The design of the ACR demands two CP antennas with left and right hand circular polarization, with a gain not lower than 10 dBi, aiming at assuring a high Radar Cross Section (RCS) of the device, with a negligible coupling between transmitting and receiving antennas. In order to achieve the CP, we make use of the perturbation of the single patch instead of using alternative rationale as the dual feed square patch with 90 degrees' phase shift, or the Sequence Rotation Array (SRA) [6]. Two kinds of perturbation have been introduced to induce field rotation on the single square patch. The first one is the corner truncated technique [7][8], in which the

orthogonal field components in phase quadrature are excited by feeding it at the center of the edge. This perturbation creates two modes with equal amplitudes whose phase difference is 90 degrees. The second technique used is the 45° diagonal slot truncation, added with the propose of reinforcing the CP generation, and improve the bandwidth of the patch antenna: using multiple slots in patches achieves a wide bandwidth response. Both techniques are based on the de-segmentation the two orthogonal modes of resonance, diagonal modes which individually yield linear polarization along the directions of the two diagonals. The antenna is designed by the use of the low cost dielectric substrate Taconic RF-30, with a thickness of 1.52mm and a nominal dielectric constant of 3. This material has a low dissipation factor, with 0.0014 value, and helps to obtain a wide bandwidth. The selected thickness assures a fine mechanical hardness, as required for the final application of the antennas.

The single patch is designed by a square with $W=14.9\text{mm}$, a 45° diagonal slot with $3.4\times 0.4\text{mm}$ dimensions, and a corner truncated with 2.9mm length. The dimensions of the patch are basically set by targeted resonant frequency: 5.405 GHz, the center frequency operated by the Sentinel1 radar. The size of the corner truncated and diagonal slot are obtained by optimizing the simulations using ANSYS HFSS [9].

Simulation Results single patch

Figure 1. Square patch (a) with corner truncated and (b) with also a diagonal slot.

There is not a great difference between the two methods when used separately to obtain the CP effect. On the contrary, the modifications introduced for obtaining CP causes a shift of resonant frequency and produces dual band frequency responses: see figure 2 where the S11 vs frequency obtained with truncated sides, with and without the diagonal slot are respectively shown. Adding the diagonal slot into the patch with corner truncated, the reflection coefficient improves.

Using the two alterations, allowed partially modifying the axial ratio (see fig.3).

Figure 2. S11 single patch with corner truncated and diagonal slot.

Figure 3. Axial Ratio patch with corner truncated and diagonal slot

Simulation Results 2x2 array

To obtain the required gain, an array composed by four patches has been designed and simulated: the scheme includes impedance matching to 50Ω , aiming at a target gain of the final antenna close to 10 dBi: see fig. 4. Fig. 5 and fig. 6 show respectively the s11, and the axial ratio, calculated for the 2x2 array. In the following figures we show: the gain value calculated along the required bandwidth, and compared to the single patch gain.

Figure 4. Array 2x2 of square patches

Finally, fig. 8a and fig. 8b show the antenna pattern calculated for the E and H plane respectively.

Figure 5. S11 calculated for the 2x2 array.

Figure 6. Axial ratio array 2x2

Figure 7. Gain array 2x2 VS single patch

Figure 8. Radiation pattern simulated for the 2x2 array, E plane (left) and H plane (right),

III. THE TEST OF THE PROTOTYPE

A prototype of the proposed array has been implemented and tested. After a first realization, which was not satisfactory due to a frequency shift with respect to the design expected in bandwidth performances, a new simulation was carried out using a value of the real dielectric constant obtained experimentally, with the implementation of a single patch element antenna. The DC estimated through the experimental approach was lower than the nominal one declared by the substrate producer, i.e. the difference is a bit larger than expected according to the nominal value from the producer is 3 ± 0.1 while the retrieved value was 2.75.

A new array was designed and a new prototype was manufactured. A picture of the last version prototype is shown in fig. 9. The antenna pattern obtained with the final, prototype is in fig. 10. Also the axial ratio has been measured and compared to simulated one: the result is shown in fig. 11. We have observed that, despite the correction of the dielectric constant used in the simulation, there is a small offset, and we need a further fitting for centering the axial ratio at the required frequency.

Fig. 9: Picture of the prototype.

Fig. 10: Antenna radiation pattern, H plane (left) and E plane (right) measured at 5.405 GHz.

Fig. 11: Axial ratio simulated, and measured, in the required bandwidth.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A 2x2 patch array aimed at providing a circular polarized antenna for Active Corner Reflector to be used with Sentinel-1 satellite data has been designed. The simulation results show a good agreement with the required operating bandwidth and axial ratio. On the other hand, the preliminary tests obtained on a manufactured prototype,

demands a bit improvement on the fabrication of the patch array. At the moment the prototype manufacturing is in progress.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This activity has been partially financed by EC within the proposal ID 776335 of the H2020 initiative Topic GALILEO-3-2017: GIMS Geodetic Integrated Monitoring System.

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